

Soumitra Sarkar*
Aryama Batabyal

Paradigm Shift of Elderly Care from Family Care to Formal Institutional Care: A Sociological Study on Old Age Homes in Hooghly District

Abstract

Care has historically had a psychosocial impact on the primary social institution of the family. Indian families are known for their sense of interdependence and coherence within the circle of the family. Household tasks were divided among the family members in the traditional joint family system. As a family, caring for the elderly was an essential duty, something they carried out generation after generation. Meanwhile, elder family members were empowered with the authority to make decisions. In today's society, however, a number of factors are changing how the family is structured and how it functions. Different forms of alternative families are growing rapidly. Numerous formal institutional forms are assuming responsibility for the care of the elderly in place of traditional forms of care due to multiple unpredictable changes. A rapid transformation is taking place in elderly care from being provided by families to being provided by institutions. Based on secondary and primary data, we discussed those possible factors that influence the transformation of care giving process. Surveys have been conducted in the Hooghly district and data has been collected from old age homes there.

Key Words: Joint family, care giving, elderly, nuclear,

Introduction

Over the last decade, elder care has shifted from family to institutional care at an astounding rate. India is estimated to have 728 old-age homes today, and 325 of them are charitable, while 95 are on a fee-for-service basis. Meanwhile, 116 of them offer free and pay-and-stay services, and no information is available for 11 (Dadidada, 2020). Generally, an old-age home is a residence for the elderly, from the age of 60 and up. Residents at these communities are often relieved of social pressures, receive hospitality, and receive health care, and, at times,

* **Soumitra Sarkar** is a Ph.D Scholar in Sociology from the Department of Sociology, University of Burdwan, West Bengal, India; **Aryama Batabyal** is a Postgraduate Student at the Jaiprakash Institute of Social Change, Vidyasagar Institute, West Bengal, India

overcome loneliness. Charitable and non-charitable old age homes are the most common forms of old age homes.

In India, several generations have traditionally lived together as a multigenerational household or joint family. The financial, physical, and emotional support that is provided through this arrangement has proven to be beneficial to all. However, nowadays the situation is changing drastically, as more joint families are becoming nuclear families. Due to medical facilities life expectancy too has increased and as a result of the social change older people have become more vulnerable.

Industrialization has put unprecedented strain on urban centers, making it financially impossible for a family to live together in larger cities. A large portion of the younger generation migrates to other cities and towns in search of a better life, education, or job opportunities, putting the elderly in jeopardy. Because of their loneliness and safety issues some widows or widowers end up in old age homes. The security and safety of an old age home protects them from intruders and in some cases, domestic abuse, allowing them to live a safe and secure life. Companionship too is one of the factors that make old age homes appealing to the elderly.

As a result, in the last few decades, the demand for old age homes has grown steadily. We conducted a thorough investigation into the perspectives of care providers for this paper. This paper focuses on the manifest and latent factors that have contributed to the rapid growth of formal elderly care facilities. This paper takes both primary and secondary data into consideration for the study.

The world's elderly population is growing at an unprecedented rate. In India, there are currently 138 million elderly people, with 194 million expected by 2031 (HelpAge, 2022). Many elderly parents are ending up in old age homes as a result of our society's massive transformation in terms of family structure over the last few decades. The proliferation of nuclear families, particularly in urban India, has resulted in an ever-increasing number of old age homes. By 2050, the world's aging population is expected to double, and the number of old age homes in India will also more than double. As the number of elderly people continues to rise, so will the demand for aged care homes. The rise of old age homes is also restructuring the social fabric

of the Hooghly District, as formal institutional care is slowly becoming the regular way of life, given the rising issues in this generation's livelihood.

Here, we have focused upon a few of the reasons that are fostering the development of this idea. In order to take care of their parents, financially secure people who relocate for work or any other reason often decide to let their parents stay in an old age home, which will look after them in exchange for payment jobs for nurses, doctors, and caregivers are more and more in demand as the number of senior living facilities rises.

Review of Literature

The Review of Literature plays a significant role in the proper implementation of any research. The researcher acquires accurate knowledge about his own research by collecting information from various previous books, journals, articles etc. Through the review of literatures the researcher has aggregated in-depth information and knowledge about the topic. Here are the details -

- ❖ Muhammad Khairul Islam (Mihammad , 2019) wrote about how the old age home, which was built to give the elderly a variety of options for enjoying their later years, has evolved into a means of evading one's parental responsibilities. He explained that the majority of elderly people end up in old age homes voluntarily after being left behind by their children when they go abroad for studies or jobs with no intention of coming back. Some people reach the old age homes after losing all their assets, which could be due to multiple reasons

- ❖ "Ei Samay Newspaper" (eisamay, 2020) discussed the argument over whether or not an old age home is a modern idea, presenting opposing points of view. Where Tilottama Majumdar stated that it is not a novel idea to force someone to live away from their family. Urnimala Basu spoke on the same topic, describing how parents help their children study abroad, wish them luck, and are proud that they will never be a burden to anyone, but in the end, when these parents age , their children neglect them, and they wind up in nursing homes. According to a quote from Badshah Maitra, "You can get

service at an old age home by pressing a bell, not love." The average life expectancy has grown, which has become a burden, added Tunal Sarkar.

- ❖ As William Butler Yeats said in "Sailing to Byzantium", "That is no country for old men" (Means & Smith, 1998). People frequently travel abroad for work in today's urban, modern world. Life is so hectic, they frequently neglect their parental responsibilities in the process. As inhumane as it may sound, that is the harsh reality of the society in which we live. As William Butler Yeats famously observed in "Sailing to Byzantium," our lives also undergo seasonal change. It is common for people to travel abroad for work in this urban, modern world, but in the process, they often neglect their parental responsibilities.
- ❖ Raquib Hasnat, A. S. M. Atipur Rahaman suggested looking at the situation of old age homes in a positive light, turning them into institutional care, not just need-based but a whole package (Kumari, Verma, & Gupta, 2016). According to this article, there are three categories of elderly people: the young elderly, who are between the ages of 60 and 70, the medium elderly, who are between the ages of 70 and 80, and the too elderly, who are above the age of 80 (Kumari, Verma, & Gupta, 2016). According to research, those between the ages of 70 and 80 suffer the most from depression, which is why they require more formal institutional care. The BBC article mentioned that the mortality rate and the fertility rate are both decreasing simultaneously while the average span of life is increasing, creating a disbalance in current society and helping the increase of old age homes. The idea expressed by Atipur Rahaman, "My old age is mine," should be accepted. The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007, stipulates that a person may be sentenced to up to six months in prison and/or a fine of up to Rs 10,000, or to both (HelpAge, 2022). Since we typically associate dietary requirements with children and mothers, elderly people need nutritious diets just as much as children do.
- ❖ Payel (2019) wrote about how the elderly often wrote off their assets to their children in hopes of being taken care of in their old age, but ended up homeless without any wealth to sustain, have to be shifted to old age homes for security (Hill, Thorn, Bowling, & Morrison, 2002). They aspire to lead fulfilling lives while maintaining their dignity and respect for themselves. In these senior living facilities, the residents are

happy because they are keeping themselves busy by watching movies, conversing with others, and participating in activities. Some singles are voluntarily relocating. "When the nuclear families started breaking up, it became a ripple effect," Kamal Hossain Doychy Veleke said.

- ❖ Children who care for the elderly are finding that the lengthening of the average life span is a problem in their daily lives (Wilson, 2000). The idea of caring for the elderly is challenging for the aging children as well because both the children and their elderly parents are aging at the same time. Elderly people risk severe abuse and mistreatment from house staff sometimes. On the other hand, old age homes are providing a solution to all of these problems, protecting the elderly, giving them shelter, and providing them with the same age companionship while taking off the pressure from the aging children's shoulders.
- ❖ In the research journal, "Economic Status of the Elderly Person: An Urban Scenario," Dr. Prashant Vishnu Sonwane mentioned that in 1995 our elderly population was 5.7 billion, but with an increase in average life span, it is expected that by 2150 the population of the elderly may reach 10.8 billion (Sonwane, 2013). Due to this, both the elderly and their social support system are extremely vulnerable to health problems. However, it is anticipated that there will be 10.8 billion elderly people in the world by the year 2150 due to an increase in the average life expectancy. Due to this, both the elderly and their social support system are extremely vulnerable to health problems. Elderly people are unnecessarily under stress and tension as a result of the decline in social, physical, and economic support. Academicians, politicians, and policymakers should conduct more thorough investigations into the economic situation and savings options for the elderly, who are frequently neglected. More emphasis should be placed on the elderly's ability to make decisions and their involvement in the economy.

Dr. Prashant Vishnu Sonwane, found that relatives, sons/daughters or spouses have a say in investments, but these elderly are also able to make independent decisions. They own a majority of urban properties. Most of them are urban property owners. They are properly cared for and maintained. The most common way of investing is through bank savings accounts, which are typically opened by elderly people. The authors of "Reason of Two Shifting People

in Old Age Home," Sonam Kumari, Mithilesh Verma, and Sangeeta Gupta, discuss how the elderly's level of education relates to their financial situation (Kumari, Verma, & Gupta, 2016). The elderly is financially suffering when they have less education, whereas when they have more education, their economic standing is improving. They are moving to this formal institutional care as a result of the social crisis, like misbehavior, abuse, indifference, and ignorance from those around them. The research journal discussed how institutional care, emotional support, and counseling may enhance their day-to-day experiences and help them lead much healthier lives for the rest of their lives, both physically and emotionally.

Research Methodology

The researchers went through some important steps in order to complete this research article. The steps taken by them are listed below.

Pilot Survey

To gain a better understanding of the social situation and issues, a pilot study was conducted before beginning the research. The study was conducted in four old age homes in the Hooghly district.

Selecting of Study Area: Hooghly district

Objectives of the Study

- To do a comparative analysis between contemporary family structure and traditional family structure in India
- To find out the causes for the shifting of care from informal family care to formal institutional care
- To execute the viewpoints of caregivers toward formal institutional care

Data Collection Tool

The interview method was used to collect data from various locations throughout the Hooghly District for this qualitative study. We prepared structured and unstructured questions within the interview schedule to obtain in-depth data from the field.

Sampling

Purposive sampling,

Sample size: 30

60:40 male to female ratio. the residents were either married couples, separated fathers, or widowers,

Major Findings

Old age home has become a reality in modern society. From the information we have gained from the survey, it is clear that for the survival of the elderly people demand of old age is increasing. pandemic. The predominance of single family is increasing and it is becoming more and more difficult for families to give proper time to the elderly. In this study, there is no intention of presenting any positive or negative picture about old age. On the other hand, there is no attempt to highlight the negative role of the family in the aging of the elderly, as in many cases there are many elderly people who have voluntarily come to old age home. There are various reasons behind the social changes that have taken place in the field of old age home in the last few decades. The study focus on two factors: the push factor and the pull factor.

Push Factors

Breakdown of traditional joint families, changes in economic structure, rapid growth of nuclear family, less important for the elderly in decision making, cultural leg and lack of social security.

Breakdown of traditional joint families: In Indian society, joint families have traditionally been responsible for caring for the elderly. As many members of the joint family live together, one or the other member shares the responsibility of caring for the elderly among themselves. But over time, there have been rigorous changes in the field of responsibility taking. Of late several members of the joint family have started migrating to different countries due to improved education, improved communication system and economic well-being (Mihammad , 2019). As a result, it is becoming increasingly difficult to maintain a traditional joint family. Elderly people are having to suffer the consequences of a comfortable life because the number of members caring for them is slowly declining in joint families.

Changes in economic structure: Changes in the economy have led to significant changes in the traditional family system. At present, the predominance of Industrial Best Economy and Service Best Economy has increased instead of agrarian economy. In modern society, as industry and service have become the dominant economy, people are moving from one place to another to join such workplaces significantly. Changes in the economic sphere have brought

about changes in the family structure as well as in the provision of appropriate services to the elderly. Individuals have moved from one place to another in search of work, which has resulted in them becoming incapable of providing services to the elderly within the family structure (eisamay, 2020). And that is why the number of old age homes as an alternative in the society is increasing with the provision of long-term services to the elderly. In many cases, older people are voluntarily choosing old age home because it is becoming more and more difficult for their children to get proper care. And that is why the number of old age homes in Indian society has increased tremendously in the last three to four decades.

Rapid growth of nuclear family: The breakdown of the joint family and the movement of the individual from one place to another in search of work is indirectly increasing the number of nuclear family. Nuclear families usually have a small number of members, and usually both spouses are working outside the home, they find it difficult to provide proper services to the elderly family members. One thing we need to keep in mind is that single families are formed but one or the other joint family breaks up (Hill, Thorn, Bowling, & Morrison, 2002). So, in a joint family where they were responsible for providing services to the elderly when the person is forming a single family but the absence of the elderly can be noticed. Most nuclear family homes in urban areas have in many cases failed to provide long-term care to the elderly. As a result, the trend of old age home in urban areas is much higher than in rural areas.

Less important for the elderly in decision making: One thing that has been noticed in traditional joint families is that older people have an important role to play in making important family decisions. They have the exclusive right to make most decisions. But over time, that is likely to change. Research has shown that as long as we were an agrarian society elderly people were playing an important role in decision making. In many cases elderly want to voluntarily settle in old age homes because the elders have lost their authority in this decision making (mane, 2016). It is seen that many older people want to live with self-esteem and they want to spend the rest of their life in old age home.

Cultural lag: The term cultural lag was generally popularized by Ogburn in Sociology. We know that cultural lag is the kind of situation when material culture starts to move faster than non-material culture which results in a gap that is usually called cultural lag. With the advancement of technology, the intensity of communication, globalization, etc., people are migrating from one place to another very easily today, which has resulted in a subtle cultural

lag centered on new technologies among the generations (Giddens, 2017). And there is a clear gap between grandparents and grandchildren due to this cultural lag. And as a result of this gap, the social relations between them are getting much weaker. So, it seems that cultural lag is weakening the bonds that traditional joint families had.

Social Security: Social security is another important push factor. The issue of social security is very important for elder people as it gives them peace of mind. Elder people in so-called joint families enjoy a lot of peace of mind because they feel much safer there. Push and pull both factors are simultaneously associated with social security. The failure of nuclear families to provide social security for the elderly pushes the elderly to move to old age homes (Lamb, 2009). Old age homes, on the other hand, provide the assurance that they are much safer because they are responsible for providing food, healthcare and other basic services over a long period of time. In urban areas, older people who are living alone in the family are exposed to a variety of social, physical and emotional abuse. In many cases some people are taking advantage of this situation and embezzling all their property and other belongings (Sarkar, 2021). There have been many incidents in urban areas where children of all families have gone out for work, even NRI families who live outside but their elderly parents stay here are facing various forms of abuse.

Pull Factors

Apart from push factors there are pull factors associated that are responsible for the growth of old age homes and transformation of care from family care to formal institutional care. Important pull factors are long-term health care, adequate food and assured shelter, facilities of recreation and healthy environment.

Long-term health care: The problem of physical problems is naturally associated with old age because older people suffer from different types of physical problems. In modern society, where the joint family has broken up into a nuclear family, there are various problems in providing long-term care to the elderly. In such a situation, old age homes are presenting themselves as responsible for providing long-term services to the elderly (Kumari, Verma, & Gupta, 2016). The provision of long-term care for both charitable and non-charitable old age homes is particularly noticeable in urban and rural areas. Currently there are a large number of

old age homes centered around providing these services that have developed in both urban and rural areas. It is also noticed that the old age homes provide medical camps and regular health checkups. At present, people's trust in old age homes is increasing due to the provision of these various facilities.

Adequate food and assured shelter: In addition to providing long-term services, the old age homes also provide adequate food and assured housing. Since old age homes are designed to provide services to the elderly, they try to prioritize three issues: health care, adequate food and housing. Not only that, the old age homes have paid a lot of attention to building the housing infrastructure in such a way keeping in mind the physical condition of the elderly and their various problems (Singh, 2017). When it comes to food, they focus on protein, vitamins and minerals i.e. a balanced diet.. On the other hand, when it comes to providing rooms for accommodation, they also notice what kind of room will be suitable for women and what kind of room will be suitable for men. Appropriate lighting, facilities of attached bathrooms, non-slippery floors, etc. are given priority while providing specific rooms to the elderly (Kant, 2021).

Facilities of recreation: In modern society, entertainment has occupied a large space in our lives. Newspapers, television, music, and other indoor and outdoor entertainment are available so that older people can spend their leisure time in peace and relaxation. Each old age home provides a variety of entertainment facilities so that older people can spend their time. Also important in this case is that the old age home attracts elder people by providing these facilities (Means & Smith, 1998). In his book, Krishna Kant tries to show that the option has become much more open to the elderly as a result of the competitive environment in the old age homes (Kant, 2021).

Healthy environment: The environmental infrastructure in the area where the old age homes are being built and even the environmental infrastructure of the old age homes have a significant impact on the mental and social life of the elderly. While researching at various old age homes in Hooghly districts, it was noticed that the issue of natural environment has been given much emphasis in the construction of old age homes. This means that the environment, climate, etc. are being considered by the old age homes while constructing. Appropriate environmental infrastructure is not just depended about the external environmental atmosphere, it is also about the internal atmosphere too (Tyagi & Paltasingh, 2015). In this context, we will

try to give importance to the attitudes, behaviors, etc. of the care providers towards the elderly people because a healthy environment is created only when the relationships between the people are much sweeter.

Discussion

Thus it has been seen that the number of old age homes is constantly increasing with several non-governmental organizations coming forward to build old age homes. On one hand, people are becoming dependent on old age homes, on the other hand, old age homes are indirectly emerging as an essential alternative for the long-term care of elderly people.

Chart: 1

Source: Created by the Authors

With the developing technology and technologically literate seniors, having access to the Internet has become a necessity. Of the old-age homes surveyed, virtually all of them had this one consistent amenity available. The primary concerns of the residents were shelter, social and physical security, and mental tranquility. Some of the old age homes for the elderly provided medical care, access to doctors who came to the facilities, and the service of transporting the elderly to hospitals when necessary.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The number of old age homes is constantly growing, and at the same time, various non-governmental organizations are stepping forward to build the old age home. On the one hand,

old age homes are becoming more and more necessary as an alternative form of long-term care for the elderly, even as some people start to become dependent on them (Rajan & Balagopal, 2017). The current body of research makes it abundantly clear that the population of paid senior living facilities is growing faster than that of charitable senior living facilities, and that public demand for paid senior living facilities is also very high. With the improvement of education, the economy, and communication systems, people are more easily moving from one place to another with their comfortable lives, education, and jobs, which is one of the major causes of the rise in elderly homes in today's world. Giving elderly family members long-term care in this circumstance is extremely difficult.

An old age home, though, need not always be viewed negatively. According to surveys, a large number of people voluntarily reside in nursing homes. The surveys of these old-age homes show that the elderly still have an independent-living mentality. On Since the old age homes offer long-term health care, regular and nutritious food , and an independent environment for the elderly to live a life of their own.

Notes

1. Babbie, E. (2022). *The Practice of Social Research*. USA: Cengage.
2. dadidada, f. (2020). *dadidadafoundation*. From [dadidadafoundation: https://dadidadafoundation.in/](https://dadidadafoundation.in/)
3. eisamay. (2020, February 9). *the-old-age-debate*. From <https://eisamay.com: https://eisamay.com/nation/the-old-age-debate/articleshow/74034281.cms>
4. Giddens, A. (2017). *Sociology*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers & Distributors Pvt Ltd.
5. HelpAge, I. (2022). *Help Them Live a Life of Dignity*. New Delhi: HelpAge India.
6. Hill, R. D., Thorn, B. L., Bowling, J., & Morrison, A. (2002). *Geriatric Residential Care*. London: LAWRENCE ERLBAUMASSOCIATES.
7. Kant, K. (2021). *Housing for Elderly and Differently Abled*. Tamil Nadu: Notion Press.
8. Kumari, S., Verma, M., & Gupta, S. (2016). Reason of the Shidting People in Old Age Home. *International Journal of Applied and Pure Science and Agriculture*, 177-180.
9. Lamb, S. (2009). *Aging and the Indian Diaspora*. USA: Indiana University Press.
10. mane, A. B. (2016). Elderly Care in India: Way Forward. *Journal of Gerontology & Geriatric Research*, 1-3.
11. Means, R., & Smith, R. (1998). *Community Care: Policy and Practice*. London: Macmillan.
12. Mihammad , K. I. (2019, November 9). *Islamik Online Media*. From <https://i-onlinemedia.net/13071: https://i-onlinemedia.net/13071>
13. Rajan, I. S., & Balagopal, G. (2017). *Elderly care in India*. Singapore: Springer.
14. Sarkar, S. (2021). Women in India: Journey and Experiance of Life of Elderly Women in the Twenty-First Century. In A. Bhowmick, & R. Sain, *Women from Tradition to Modernity* (pp. 327-340). New Delhi: Mittal Publication.
15. Singh, A. (2017). *Old Age Homes: India and Abroad*. Jaipur: Book Enclave.

16. Sonwane, P. V. (2013). Economic status of the Elderly person: An Urban Scenario. *Research Way*, 10-17.
17. Tyagi, R., & Paltasingh, T. (2015). Aging Well and Way Forward. In T. Paltasingh, & R. Tyagi, *Caring for the Elderly* (pp. 264-280). New Delhi: Sage.
18. Victor, C. R. (1994). *Old Age in Modern Society*. Malaysia: Chapman & Hall.
19. Wilson, G. (2000). *Understanding Old Age: Critical and Global Perspectives*. London: Sage.